

**The Third Half: creating healthy and supporting research environments at the
Autonomous University of Barcelona**

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Abstract

It is suggested that early career researchers' (ECRs) are a risk population to develop mental health problems related to stress, burnout or anxiety and depression. In response to this alarming situation and following the European Research Area policies regarding researchers' wellbeing, the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) started working towards the creation of mentally healthier research environments, since a 50% of doctoral candidates showed anxiety and a 45%, moderate to severe symptoms of depression after the Covid-19 pandemic. The Social Responsibility Unit and the Doctoral School contacted the Core Mental Health Unit and coordinated local research teams working on wellbeing promotion to design and implement action plans towards mental health prevention at the UAB. Among other actions, an innovative prevention program was designed and tested among ECRs: the Third Half. The name refers to a rugby tradition in which the players meet after the match in a more informal environment to spend some more time together with the rivals and colleagues having a drink and promoting friendship and fair play. It was framed within the motivational model of self-determination and the humanistic principles of education, where unconditional acceptance is a key principle of the learning process. The activity was announced in the UAB's website and an e.mail was sent to all Ph.D. candidates to ask for participation. Although 80 ECRs applied for the activity in only 5 days after its announcement, just 25 could participate in the pilot study. It consisted in six gamified outdoor sessions of 3 hours each, delivered once a month in outdoor-green spaces, and guided by 2 researchers-psychologists specialized in gamification, coaching and Positive Psychology. A pre-post design of repeated measures showed significant increases in almost all motivation and wellbeing indicators, while significant decreases in anxiety and negative affect were also obtained. Internal quality assessment showed that participants' satisfaction levels with the intervention were very high. Given these positive results, the Doctoral School will implement the Third Half as a permanent and cost-effective activity next academic year 2022-23 with the collaboration of specific units of training, research and intervention on wellbeing and mental health. The goal is to implement ERA policies by involving and rewarding local researchers, able to facilitate knowledge transfer on wellbeing interventions and to ultimately create healthier and more supporting research environments at the UAB.

Keywords: mental health; wellbeing; early career researchers; institutional interventions; positive psychology

Introduction

Over the last few years, various reports have shown evidence of the worsening well-being and mental health among Ph.D. and early career researchers (ECR) working in the European Research Area (ERA; Kismihok et al., 2021, 2022). Although the data indicates that the young researchers are very satisfied and motivated by their learning process, the data also shows that before the COVID-19 pandemic, between 32% and 42% of ECRs were at risk of developing mental health problems, being depression, anxiety, burnout or cognitive exhaustion, the most frequent disorders among the academic community, who present a higher risk than the general population of suffering mental health complications (Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Sorrel et al., 2020). It is estimated that the number of doctoral students with mental illness is 2.84 times higher than the number of adults with a high level of education in general. (Levecque et al., 2017). This trend has also been seen in Catalan universities, where research staff with temporary contracts have worse physical and mental health, more stress symptoms, and are less satisfied with their jobs than both full-time professors and researchers with stable contracts (Cladellas et al., 2018). A situation that has worsened during the COVID-19 pandemic (Naumann et al., 2022; Pyhältö et al., 2022), also in Catalan universities (Sanz, 2022), where a 45% of the academic community presents anxious-depressive symptoms, a prevalence that is 9 points higher than in the general population. In line with previous studies, the incidence among undergraduate and post-graduate students is the highest (54%), compared to permanent teaching and research staff (25%). Recently, another study at the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) has confirmed this alarming data (Muro et al., 2022), indicating that a 47% of ECRs are at risk of suffering anxious disorders, while a 45% shows moderate to severe clinical depressive symptoms. This situation follows the European tendency (Kismihok et al., 2021), and calls for research staffs, institutions, funding bodies, stakeholders, and governments to work together to overcome the so-called "Ph.D. crisis" and encourage investments in promoting healthier research careers that enhance the wellbeing, not only of doctoral students, but of the entire research, and academic community (Evans et al., 2018; Guthrie et al., 2017; Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Woolston, 2017). Most university research outcomes and excellence levels depend on the work and contributions of ECRs who often represent more than 50% of university teams (Horta et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2020; Norton et al., 2018) and play a fundamental role in

economic growth, innovation and the advancement of knowledge in universities and countries of the European Union (OECD, 2019). Although future doctors will be highly qualified professionals who will work in research centres, R&D companies, governments and administrations, and will be key personnel to find solutions and make decisions on political, technical, social, and medical issues, their technical specialization and the development of their talent primarily depend on competitively funded projects, creating a professional uncertainty not seen in other labour sectors. A recent example is the COVID-19 pandemic, during which thousands of young researchers from many fields are still developing strategies and innovations for the discovery of new vaccines, for the reconstruction of economies, health systems and social support structures worldwide. Despite this specialisation, low salaries, contractual uncertainty, the workload and complexity of the work, the high level of specialization required and job insecurity, added to the pressure to publish or the lack of institutional support or funding to lead projects, end up taking a toll on both their professional performance and their mental health (Kismihok et al., 2022; Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Skopek et al., 2022; van Rooij et al., 2021). This situation leads to significant academic dropouts (Castelló et al., 2017), indicating how, in Spanish universities, a third of active doctoral students drop out of doctoral training. However, it is estimated that, on an international level, the current dropout prevalence ranges from 50% to 70%, and in some cases, it has been observed that only 10% complete doctoral training (van Rooij et al., 2021). The main reasons point to the difficulty of reconciling doctoral studies with personal and professional life (25%) and to social isolation, demotivation or lack of institutional support (40%) (Castelló et al., 2017; Skopek et al., 2022).

For these reasons, the creation and implementation of psychoeducational programs to promote wellbeing and the talent of young researchers in doctoral studies is a strategic priority for the ERA and a long-sought demand by the entire community of European and international Ph.D. students (EURODOC, 2021; Kismihók et al. 2022; Metcalfe et al., 2022; O'Neill & Schroijsen, 2018; Remo, 2021). These interventions and prevention programs should offer cost-benefit strategies that a) facilitate their well-being and optimal psychosocial development, and that b) improve their motivation to reduce the risks associated with the dropout rates of the research career. But while it is necessary to promote and generalize psychoeducational programs that complement technical training to reach more optimal health levels and professional excellence, it is first necessary to

create synergies of institutional collaboration and coordinate administrative teams, professors and researchers to implement actions at a local level. These actions should promote and guarantee more motivating and healthy research environments in order to improve upskilling in well-being and health, institutions' cohesion, teamwork and psychosocial support, emotional regulation of stress and burnout, and, ultimately, to improve the organizational culture and working climate where young researchers develop (Castelló et al., 2017; Metcalfe et al., 2022; OMS, 2020; ReMo, 2021; Sorrel et al., 2020).

While it is true that European and institutional policies are slowly reorienting doctoral training, more regional and local investments are needed in order to implement sustainable services that favour the well-being and development of researchers in their workplace. These training services are not yet widespread in the ERA, in part because their implementation depends mostly on grants and projects to implement these changes (Kismihok et al., 2021, 2022). Therefore, the implementation of these policies at the local level is a challenge for the entire research community and should go a step further: university managers at the local level should invest in prioritizing psychoeducational services within the doctoral programs (with the collaboration of research teams and specialized professors from each university) to work together to build healthier research environments and learning environments that are more motivating and favourable for the well-being and global development of young researchers (ReMo, 2022).

In this context of implementing welfare and mental health policies, it is worth noting the efforts at the UAB, one of the main public universities in Catalonia and Spain, recognized with the distinction of "HR Excellence in Research". During the last few years, following the guidelines of the European Charter and the Code of Conduct (European Commission, 2021), different administration teams at the UAB have been working on the implementation of services aimed at improving the well-being, motivation and development of researchers. The creation of a specific Social Responsibility unit that works to promote improvements toward a Sustainable and Healthy Campus (UAB, 2022a), has implemented several actions that, in collaboration with other units such as the CORE in Mental Health (UAB, 2022b) have facilitated the coordination of specific actions between various teaching and research teams specialized in promoting health and emotional well-being. This type of intervention is a

top priority for European university policies that try to meet the goals for sustainable development set by the UN and the WHO (UN, 2022; WHO, 2022).

In this framework of institutional collaboration at the UAB, and in response both to the alarming data on mental health in doctoral students and to the European policies to promote well-being in universities, the Social Responsibility Unit, the Doctoral School and the Unit of Coaching and Support for Academics (UAB, 2022c) started working together to promote, in the 2021-22 academic year, various actions to promote emotional well-being. One of them was specifically designed as a pilot action to improve the well-being and psychosocial support of doctoral students: the Third Half (UAB, 2022d).

Methods

In October 2021, the Social Responsibility- Campus SIS unit and School of Doctorate contacted the CORE Mental Health Unit to meet those teams and researchers experts in the promotion and design of mental health prevention and wellbeing programs in educational settings. From the various research teams and teachers contacted at the UAB Campus, a response was obtained from the UCAA (UAB, 2022c). It was agreed to design and implement a psycho-educational action to increase the well-being, motivation and mental health of ECRs as a pilot study during the second semester of the 2021-22 academic year: the Third Half.

Design and procedure

Originally, the *Third Half* refers to a moral tradition in rugby and sports, where at the end of the match, rivals gather to share some time together and have a drink or eat something, as an excuse to fraternize and ease any resentment that could have arisen during the match. The Third Half is as important or more important than the match itself, because it is where the players learn to manage their emotions, respect their rivals and teammates, and thus manage the hostilities that the game has produced for them, establishing cordial relationships and friendship as a result of their shared experience in this sport. With the same purpose, the UCAA adapted this practice for the design of the psychoeducational intervention for doctoral students by hosting monthly meetings between doctoral students at the UAB Campus.

Characteristics:

Frequency and duration: 6 monthly sessions of 3 hours each (from February to July).

Structure: The first 2 hours consist in activities aimed at promoting well-being in outdoor spaces on the Campus and the third hour - more informal - aims to facilitate social connection and peer support by having a drink or a snack in one of the bars or cafes of the UAB.

Trainers: Ph.D. psychologists and specialists in motivation and academic well-being. For this pilot study, there was a full-time professor, Ph.D. specialist in Positive Psychology and Coaching that designed and lead the activity with the collaboration of the Doctoral program in Health and Sports Psychology (UAB, 2022e), that chose and facilitated a doctoral candidate and psychologist specialized in gamification, to give support both in the design of the activity and its implementation. This Ph.D. candidate acted as a peer-mentor, while the professor acted as a coach and coordinated all the activity with the participants and UAB units involved. Both trainers had to speak English in case there were international ECRs. The coach also contacted the ReMO researchers at the UAB (ReMO, 2021) to inform and invite them to participate in the activity. One ReMO researcher participated in some sessions of the activity and was included in the participating group.

Objectives: 1) to increase motivation and emotional well-being and 2) to improve psychosocial and institutional support and reduce risks associated to mental health complications in UAB doctoral students.

Method: to create a space and time to play, talk and reflect among peers and facilitate the connection between doctoral students, creating an informal environment that is more motivating and emotionally healthy, without adding more workloads or stress to the participants. It was designed to be delivered in Catalan, Spanish and English once a month.

Criteria for the design of the activity: The design of the activity followed the criteria of the World Health Organisation (2022) and the ReMO's (2022) peer-mentoring recommendations. However, given that the teaching and research team of the UCAA is specialized in the promotion of well-being, the prevention of mental health and in the development of talent (UCAA, 2022), additional criteria were included to design this psychosocial support action for UAB doctoral students.

The 5 main criteria for the design of Third Half were the following:

- 1- **Gamified activities** (Huan & Soman, 2013; Kiriakova et al., 2014; Nah et al., 2018). Gamification is a strategy for applying game principles, defined as the integration of game elements into non-game activities, using mechanics, aesthetics, and thinking to engage people, motivate action, and promote learning and problem solving in a funny way (Kapp, 2012). It is effective in educational processes (Manzano-León et al., 2021) by improving motivation and learning in formal and informal conditions.
- 2- **Outdoor activities and green spaces** (Gilbertson et al., 2022; Muro et al., 2022). Outdoor learning, defined as "that which lies beyond the walls of the interior", has been shown to provide more meaningful, deep and stimulating learning experiences that facilitate interest and motivation to learn. It is often considered that outdoor learning can provide opportunities in many subjects and also support students' personal, social and emotional development. On the other hand, it has also been shown that exposure to green and natural environments immediately facilitates relaxation and emotional well-being, and therefore promotes the comprehensive health of individuals. The location of the Third Half alternated different outdoor and green spaces of the Campus: the Central Axis-Campus SIS, the Knowledge Square, the Agora of the Auditorium of the Faculty of Arts and Philosophy and different green spaces between the Faculties of Sciences and Social Sciences.
- 3- **Positive Psychology and Coaching applied in Educational Settings** (Grant, 2008, 2022; Green & Norrish, 2013; Muro et al., 2018; Palmer & Whybrow, 2008; Vázquez & Hervás, 2018; Whitmore et al., 2013). The activity was framed within the framework of Positive Psychology applied in education for the prevention and promotion of psychological well-being. We used exercises specific to interventions based on Positive Psychology targeted at the academic non-clinical population such as practising gratitude, savoring, acceptance or mindfulness. Techniques widely used in Coaching Psychology and specific to Education were also used, such as Socratic maieutic or asking questions and conversations towards improvement and growth, setting goals with the Grow method, or the visualizations applied to personal improvement and coping with life crises.

- 4- **Physical activity** (Pallarès et al., 2020; Tyson et al. 2010). It is well known that the practice of a physical activity is a protective factor for mental health at all stages of development and especially for students. It has been shown how a lack of physical activity worsens health, both physical and mental, and is considered a key cost-benefit strategy in policies to promote well-being. Although the goal was not to make a physical activity training program, typical games that encourage behavioural activation, as those played in the school yards, teamwork and cooperation were proposed, such as: passing the ball, handkerchief game, relays, etc.
- 5- **Peer mentoring and peer support** (Kismihok et al., 2022; Lorenzetti et al., 2019). In conventional mentoring, the student is matched with someone more senior in the organization or who has more experience in a particular area of interest. There is often an expectation of professional development. In peer mentoring, the mentor is usually someone with a similar background, just a little more advanced academically, and who can bring an alternative perspective to the career path. The additional social support that allows the student to share their worries, concerns or conflicts also facilitates their performance and emotional well-being, while fostering bonds of friendship between the participants. The mentor offers space and time for reflection and dialogue, listens and guides; collective mentoring, it also facilitates peer connection and diminishes feelings of social isolation, promoting a shared learning experience that simultaneously facilitates identification with others, friendship, altruism and mutual aid.

Finally, it should be noted that all the activity was framed within the motivational model of self-determination (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and the humanistic principles of education, where unconditional acceptance or non-judgment are key principles for learning processes (Khatib et al., 2013; Rogers, 1985; Sharp, 2012; Stober, 2006; Treve, 2021).

To read a more detailed description of each session, see the Third Half: Design and Implementation booklet (Muro & Bonilla, 2022).

Design and procedure

On January 25, 2022, a call was made for participation in the Thid Half, announcing it in the UAB's website [activity on the UAB website](#) and sending an email to all Ph.D. students of the UAB Campus through the mailing list of the School of Doctorate. In just

5 days, 80 applications were obtained, but only 40 Ph.D. students could be registered, according to the human resources available to implement this pilot study.

Participants answered a battery of questionnaires designed to know and contrast their levels of emotional well-being and motivation before and after starting the activity. The pre-survey made it possible to contrast the profiles of the participants with a sample of doctoral students who did not participate in the third time to find out if they were comparable to the rest of the doctoral students at the UAB. An item was also included to identify the possible presence of chronic or serious pathologies, and thus to be able to adapt the activities in case of having Ph.D. students with functional diversity or other significant disorders that affected mobility. On the other hand, the results obtained before starting the activity (February 2022) were contrasted with a post measure at the end of the intervention (July 2022) to evaluate the impact of the Third Time on the participants' emotional well-being and motivation. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, and participants were informed about the use of the data for solely scientific and research purposes. The study was approved by the Doctoral School, and by the Campus-SIS Unit of the UAB Vice-Rectorate.

Participants

After 5 days after the official announcement of the activity, 80 registration requests were obtained, but according to the resources to implement this pilot study, only 40 participants could be accepted (in order of registration). After sending more detailed information and once confirmation of participation was received, a total of 25 Ph.D. students attended the first session, of which 10 (40%) attended all sessions, 9 (36%) attended only the first 3, and 6 (24%) attended intermittently to the sessions of the Third Half. In this pilot study, none of the participants reported illnesses or significant disorders that affected their health and mobility, so none of the activities had to be adapted. However, it should be noted that the activities were voluntary and there was no obligation to do them for the participants; in any case, alternative activities were contemplated for the participation of Ph.D. students who could not do some of the scheduled activities.

Finally, of the 25 participants, 18 answered all the pre- and post-questionnaires and were included in the analyses. The average age was 31 years ($ds = 6.90$; minimum = 25, maximum = 53), while 67% were women and 44% were international Ph.D. students.

83% were single, and the remaining 17% were married or in a stable partnership. The representation according to the field of knowledge can be seen in Table 1.

Instruments

A brief survey was designed and administered to investigate the socio-demographic profile of the participants, their levels of emotional well-being and satisfaction with the doctoral training process, their relationship with their supervisor, and their academic motivation toward the completion of their dissertation. This survey was designed in collaboration with several researchers from the Faculty of Psychology who participated voluntarily in its design. The survey was sent to the UAB's doctoral students through an e-mail from the Doctoral School requesting participation, attaching a Googleforms online. Six valid and reliable questionnaires, widely used in research on emotional well-being, were administered:

1. State and Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI; Riquelme y Casal, 2011): This test measures state (at the moment) and trait (global personality) anxiety levels with a total of 20 items in each scale and format of Likert-type responses. High scores indicate anxiety-related changes in mood, while low scores show emotional stability and the lack of anxiety. In this case, we only administered the state anxiety scale.

2. Brief Scale of Emotional Profiles (Profile of Mood States - POMS; Andrade et al., 2013). This test measures 6 moods based on 30 items: Anger, Fatigue, Vigor, Friendship, Tension, and Depression which must be scored from 0 to 5. They are emotional states, and therefore are variable and reactive to situations and context. Even though they can be indicators of possible psycho-pathologies, they have no clinical value and only show emotional profiles at the time they are measured.

3. Positive and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS; López-Gómez, Hervás & Vázquez, 2015): Includes two subscales of 10 items each that assess the pattern of experiencing positive emotions related to psychological well-being and the experience of negative emotions related to psychological discomfort.

4. Maslach Burnout Inventory Scale (MBI; Maslach & Jackson, 1981): The professional exhaustion syndrome, also called the burnout syndrome, is a suffering that would broadly consist of the presence of a prolonged stress response in the organism in the face of emotional and interpersonal factors that present themselves at work. It

includes chronic fatigue, ineffectiveness and denial of what has happened. It includes 3 subscales measured with 22 items that explore: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal fulfilment. Some items were adapted to the research work environment.

5. General Anxiety Disorder-2 (GAD2; García-Campayo, et al., 2012): It measures briefly and allows screening to detect the possible presence of symptoms associated with Generalized Anxiety Disorder. The scale consists of 2 items. A Likert-type response scale is used to assess the presence of symptoms in the previous two weeks. The final score is calculated by adding the scores of the 2 items. The scores can range from 0 to 6, and it can be used to make a preliminary diagnosis: no anxiety disorder (0–2) or possible anxiety disorder (3–6).

6. Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ9; Kroenke et al., 2001): The PHQ-9 items follow the nine criteria specified in the DSM-IV diagnostic manual for screening for depressive disorder. A Likert-type scale is used to explore whether symptoms have been present in the last two weeks. Depending on frequency ("not at all", "several days", "more than half the days", and "almost every day"), the nine items are scored from 0 to 3 points with a maximum total of 27 points. When the total score is between 10 and 14, 15 to 19, or 20 to 27, it means that the depressive symptoms are moderate, moderately severe, or severe, respectively.

7. Additionally, **5 ad-hoc items** were designed to find out the levels of Ph.D. motivation (including motivation with the thesis, the motivation perceived by the supervisor and by the team), the relationship with the supervisor, and the satisfaction with the doctoral training process, each item with a Likert-type scale with response ranges from 0 to 5 points. Only the motivation items were added to the post measures. The three variables were categorized, indicating scores <3 as unsatisfactory and >2 as satisfactory.

8. Lastly, there were two questions about the doctoral students' health. These questions asked if they had any long-term illnesses, functional diversity, including mobility problems, in order to consider them and adapt the design of the Third Half activities.

Statistical analysis and quality assessment

Means (and standard deviations) were calculated for each indicator of emotional well-being and the frequencies (percentages) of participants' sociodemographics.

Analyses of variance (ANOVA) were first performed to check if there were baseline differences based on gender, age, family situation, field of knowledge, and type of doctoral program (international/national). They were also contrasted with those of a wider sample of doctoral students who did not participate in the Third Half. Next, the non-parametric Wilcoxon repeated-measure test was used, due to the small sample size, to analyse pre-post changes before and after the activity, and thus explore the impact of the intervention on the different indicators of emotional well-being and motivation of the participants. Additionally, an internal quality assessment was performed, calculating the prevalence of responses to ad-hoc designed questions and measuring the level of satisfaction with the learning process according to the 5 criteria of the activity design: motivation, social connectedness, methods and techniques used, emotional well-being, and research perspective. All analyses were calculated with the statistical program SPSS 20.0.0.

Results

The descriptive statistics of the sample can be seen in Table 1. In the ANOVA, no significant differences were found in the different indicators of well-being according to gender, family situation, field of knowledge, or type of program (international/national).

Table 1. Sociodemographic and scientific profile of the Third Half participants.

Gender	<i>N</i>	%
Man	6	33,3
Woman	12	66,7
Non-binary	0	0
Family status		
Single	15	83,3
Married or in a stable relationship	3	17
With children	1	1
Field of knowledge		
Health Sciences	6	33,3
Life sciences	4	22,2
Experimental sciences	2	11,1
Social Sciences	2	11,1
Arts and Humanities	3	16,7
Engineering and Architecture	1	5,6
International		
No	10	55,6
Yes	8	44,4

The profile of the Third Half participants was representative and comparable to the rest of the doctoral students at the UAB, but with slight differences in their initial levels

regarding the relationship with the supervisor ($F = 5.07$; $p = .026$), the satisfaction with the learning process ($F = 4.07$; $p = .045$), the perceived motivation from the team ($F = 11.55$; $p = .001$) and the global motivation for completing the doctoral dissertation ($F = 5.85$; $p = .017$), showing lower scores in the Third Half group. Third Half's participants also showed significantly higher scores on POMS' depression scale before starting the activity when compared to the non-participants ($F = 4.32$; $p = .039$) (see Table 2). A prevalence of 50% in generalized anxiety symptoms was observed among the participants before starting the activity, similar and comparable to the 53% of non-participants ($\chi^2 = 0.90$; $p = .765$). Clinical depression prevalence were also similar and comparable among groups, showing 45% of moderate to severe symptoms in the Third Half participants, and a 40% among non-participants ($\chi^2 = 5.81$; $p = .213$).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of motivation and well-being indicators of the Third Half participants compared with a control group of non-participants

	Third Half				<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
	NO (<i>n</i> = 140)		YES (<i>n</i> = 25)			
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Age	30,94	6,79	33,24	7,82	2,93	,088
Relationship with the supervisor	4,99	1,76	4,24	1,67	5,07	,026
Satisfaction with the learning process	2,54	,99	2,15	1,13	4,07	,045
Motivation						
Thesis motivation	3,43	1,15	3,15	,86	1,81	,180
Supervisor's motivation	3,32	1,31	3,12	,94	,691	,407
Team motivation	2,99	1,34	2,15	1,07	11,55	,001
Total motivation	9,74	3,04	8,41	1,97	5,85	,017
STAI_Anxiety (State)	30,19	12,85	34,59	10,03	3,45	,065
POMS						
Anger	25,97	11,84	26,82	10,62	,15	,698
Vigour	8,564	4,61	8,059	4,16	,34	,560
Friendship	14,36	4,00	14,35	4,35	,00	,988
Tension	9,11	5,81	9,41	5,02	,07	,779
Depression	6,31	5,04	8,38	5,80	4,32	,039
PANAS						
Positive Affect	29,98	8,20	29,09	7,99	,32	,569
Negative Affect	22,01	8,79	24,47	8,98	2,13	,146
MBI						
Emotional exhaustion	25,97	11,84	26,82	10,62	,14	,702
Depersonalization	8,41	6,28	9,41	6,78	,66	,415
Personal fulfilment	27,42	8,41	25,68	8,19	1,18	,278
GAD2_Anxiety	2,64	2,03	2,44	1,87	,25	,613
% with 2 symptoms	53%		50%			
PHQ_Depression	9,01	6,65	10,00	5,77	,62	,431
% without symptoms	29%		15%			

% slight	31%	30%
% moderate to severe	40%	45%

Notes: STAI- State Trait Anxiety Inventory; POMS- Profile of Mood States; PANAS- Positive and Negative Affect Scale; MBI- Maslach Burnout Inventory; GAD- General Anxiety Disorder; PHQ- Patient Health Questionnaire.

Table 3. Wilcoxon test to contrast measures of motivation and emotional wellbeing before and after the Third Half

Motivation		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p</i>
Thesis				3,24	,001
PRE		3,59	,87		
POST		5,00	1,02		
Supervisor				3,12	,002
PRE		2,94	,72		
POST		3,67	,84		
Research team				2,14	,032
PRE		1,94	1,21		
POST		2,83	1,24		
Global motivation				3,51	,000
PRE		8,00	2,00		
POST		11,33	1,81		
STAI State Anxiety				3,19	,001
PRE		36,22	8,78		
POST		21,22	12,40		
POMS					
Anger	PRE	8,61	6,31	2,38	,017
	POST	4,94	3,90		
Fatigue	PRE	13,28	6,34	2,25	,024
	POST	8,44	6,20		
Vigour	PRE	7,06	4,19	3,00	,003
	POST	12,61	4,11		
Friendship	PRE	13,44	3,01	2,39	,017
	POST	15,44	2,12		
Tension	PRE	10,61	5,68	1,89	,059
	POST	6,83	5,00		
Depression	PRE	9,22	4,18	3,57	,000
	POST	3,50	3,31		
PANAS					
Positive Affect				3,20	,001
PRE		25,78	7,55		
POST		34,72	7,45		
Negative Affect				2,22	,026
PRE		26,61	9,61		
POST		19,33	8,06		
MBI					
Emotional exhaustion				1,61	,107
PRE		30,17	9,69		
POST		23,94	7,74		
Depersonalization				,39	,690
PRE		9,44	6,12		
POST		9,27	5,19		
Personal fulfilment				1,51	,130
PRE		23,71	8,06		
POST		26,94	7,28		
PHQ_Depression				1,58	,114
PRE		9,35	5,53		
POST		6,16	3,85		
GAD2_Anxiety				3,03	,002
PRE		3,11	1,56		
POST		1,50	,92		

Notes: STAI- State Trait Anxiety Inventory; POMS- Profile of Mood States; PANAS- Positive and Negative Affect Scale; MBI- Maslach Burnout Inventory; GAD- General Anxiety Disorder; PHQ- Patient Health Questionnaire.

Table 4. Frequencies and percentages of participants with clinical symptoms of depression and anxiety

Anxiety GAD2	Pre		Post	
Without symptoms	12	67%	18	100%
With symptoms	6	33%	0	0%
Depression PHQ9				
Without symptoms	3	17%	6	33%
Slight	6	33%	9	50%
Moderate	6	33%	3	17%
Moderate to severe	1	6%	0,0	0%
Severe	1	6%	0,0	0%

Notes: GAD2- General Anxiety Disorder; PHQ9- Patient Health Questionnaire

Internal quality assessment of the learning process

The descriptive statistics of each item formulated for the evaluation of the internal quality of the learning process can be consulted in Table 4, with 0 being the minimum and 5 the maximum satisfaction rating. The range of values of each item varied between 3.71 and 4.96, thus obtaining a satisfactory assessment in all the quality criteria that were used to design the activity. After categorizing the responses into two levels (satisfied/not satisfied) and grouping the items into five broad scales (emotional well-being, motivation, perspective of the research career, social support, and methods/structure), a 100% of participants were satisfied with the impact on their motivation, a 93% with the impact on their emotional well-being, and a 50% with the impact on their social support.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of internal quality assessment's items

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
item1_increasedMOTIVATION	2	5	3,86	1,167
item2_increasedPERSPECTIVE	2	5	3,71	1,139
item3_helpedcopingwithCareer	2	5	3,86	1,167
item4_increasedPositiveEmotions	0	5	3,93	1,439
item5_feltsocialSupport	3	5	4,64	,745
item6_increasedemotionalWellbeing	3	5	4,21	,802
item7_decreasedisolation	1	5	4,36	1,277
item8_enjoyedgamifiedapproach	1	5	4,21	1,311
item9_outdoorapproach	3	5	4,86	,535
item10_enjoyedgroupapproach	3	5	4,64	,633
item11_enjoyedforestbathing	4	5	4,96	1,791
item12_stablishedgoals	2	5	3,93	,997
item13_increasedsocialConnectedness	2	5	4,29	1,069
item14_feltrespectedandValued	3	5	4,64	,745
item15_goodcoachs	3	5	4,64	,633
item16_recommendtheactivity	4	5	4,79	,426

item17_feltmoremotivated	2	5	4,29	1,069
item18_increasedmywellbeingHealth	2	5	4,07	1,072
item19_increasedmyselfKnowledge	2	5	4,36	1,008
item20_feelingpartofReseachcommunity	2	5	4,36	,929

Discussion and conclusions

The Third Half, as a mental-health prevention program carried out at the UAB, is one of the first action plans in the universities of the European Research Area (ERA) led by an institutional initiative following recommendations on mental health policies, executed by local teams of experts in motivation and emotional well-being from the same organization. The design of the intervention as a local-institutional action has facilitated the transfer of knowledge and at the same time applied research within the university itself. It is a long-standing demand by ERA doctoral students (Eurodoc, 2021; Kismihok et al., 2021, 2022) and it should be noted that the results have been satisfactory, not only in terms of the results on the effectiveness of the intervention, but also in terms of the positive experience of coordination between the different local teams involved.

In line with previous studies (Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Sorrel et al., 2020; Kismihok et al., 2022), the data shows that the ECRs at UAB are satisfied and motivated with their work, but between 41% and 47% have symptoms of depression and anxiety, respectively. The results observed during the COVID-19 pandemic in the general university population have also been replicated, since the incidence of depression and anxiety was between 45% and 54% (Sanz, 2022). However, while it is true that these indicators are alarming, the relevance of this study relies on the positive results of Third Half intervention, since a significant improvement has been observed in Ph.D.s' wellbeing and motivation participating in the activity. On the one hand, significant increases were observed after the intervention in all motivation indicators (including Ph.D.s' perceived motivation of the supervisors and research teams), vigour, friendship and positive affect, while significant reductions were obtained in anxiety, anger, fatigue, and depression, as well as in negative affect and symptoms of generalized anxiety disorder. Even though statistical significance was not reached yet, it's important to point out the observed decreases in depressive symptoms, burnout, and the number of people at risk of having severe depression.

These numbers show that this kind of cost-benefit intervention should be used and studied more in Catalan universities, and they should be taken into account to keep

researchers from getting mentally or emotionally hurt on the job. The results motivate us to continue working together to overcome the so-called "Ph.D. crisis" and promote healthier research careers, as well as to develop specific actions that promote the mental health, not only of doctoral students, but of the entire research and academic community of the ERA after the Covid-19 pandemic (Evans et al., 2018; Guthrie et al., 2017; Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Woolston, 2017).

In this way, initiatives like the Third Half, designed following quality criteria and by experts in mental health - could be a cost-effective solution from universities to offer institutional support for the academic performance and integral development of younger researchers (Kismihok et al., 2022; Lau & Pretorius, 2019; Skopek et al., 2022; van Rooij et al., 2021). Initiatives like this could not only reduce the incidence of mental health problems among ECRs, but also increase academic motivation, and therefore, reduce the prevalence of drop-outs or doctoral students who abandon the doctoral career, which is estimated to be between 50% and 70% in the ERA, with some studies indicating that only 10% complete doctoral training, showing the hard path to complete the doctoral process (Castelló et al., 2017; van Rooij et al., 2021). It should be noted that the intervention axes of the Third Half have been designed with the fundamental objective of reducing social isolation and demotivation, which are the main risks for depression and anxiety, by offering free and expert psychological support, hidden in funny gamified outdoor activities. It has been an intervention well valued by the doctoral students, as indicated by the data on the internal quality of the process, with satisfaction indicators that validate the results obtained on its efficacy. There was almost a 100% of satisfaction in the assessment of the internal quality regarding the different psychosocial objectives set out in the Third Half: to increase participants' emotional well-being, to increase motivation, and decrease social isolation through the use of evidence-based methods for the collective management of researchers' well-being. It should be remembered that social isolation and demotivation, but also the lack of institutional support, are the key-factors that the Third Half aimed to address, since they have been worsened during the Covid-19 pandemic, especially among international ECRs, and since these factors explain a 40% of dropouts from doctoral studies (Castelló et al., 2017; Skopek et al., 2022).

For these reasons, it is concluded that the creation and pilot implementation of the Third Half has been satisfactory and has been effective in responding to the strategic

challenges of the ERA and to the demands of the European Ph.D. students (EURODOC, 2021; Kismihók et al. 2022; Metcalfe et al., 2022; O'Neill & Schroijen, 2018; Remo, 2021). This intervention has demonstrated its effectiveness in improving the psychosocial support, motivation and wellbeing of ECRs. Although it still presents sample limitations and thus, limitations regarding the generalizability of the results, the results encourage further research to analyse this psychoeducational intervention since it might be a good cost-effective strategy to reduce the risks of the research career associated with mental health, motivation, and emotional wellbeing. This type of actions could facilitate upskilling in stress and burnout regulation, communication and social skills, teamwork, and ultimately, in the creation of a healthier organizational culture and working climate where young researchers develop (Castelló et al., 2017; Metcalfe et al., 2022; OMS, 2020; Sorrel et al., 2020). The results encourage the implementation of the Third Half in the following academic year to reach a wider range of ECRs and to offer it as an optional certified activity in the UAB doctoral programmes. Its implementation will also offer alternatives to enhance the methodological design and overcome the present limitations, that point to the need of a) including a control group to compare the pre-post design, b) widening the sample and number of participants of different fields and characteristics, c) including randomisation techniques or d) adapting the Third Half to other cultural backgrounds to contrast and generalise its results with different trainers and mentors.

The voluntary efforts of the several university teams have indeed facilitated this intervention; however, additional institutional efforts and investments in structuring and standardizing actions are required to facilitate permanent and sustainable psychoeducational services that promote the optimal development of researchers in the workplace over time. These training services are not yet widespread in the ERA, in part because their implementation depends primarily on researchers' personal motivations, grants and projects and not on the effective implementation of mental health promotion policies at a local level (Kismihok et al., 2022; Metcalfe et al., 2022; ReMO, 2022). Besides, despite the fact that some pioneering universities such as the UAB are responding to European policies at a local level, efforts must continue to be made to guarantee the implementation of the European Charter and the Code of Conduct for Researchers (European Commission, 2021). More generalized structural actions are still needed, prioritizing the implementation of psychosocial support services within doctoral

programs, lead by administrative staffs and with its corresponding local investments to face the economic costs and the human resources needed to implement them. The goal is collective and systemically affects all the ERA community, thus it is important to continue working together to build healthier research and learning environments for the well-being and optimal development of the research community at a local level after the Covid-19 pandemic (ReMO, 2021). Therefore, it could be possible to continue progressing toward the promotion of well-being and prevention in mental health in Higher Education, as a priority of the sustainable development goals, set at a global-international level by the European Commission, the United Nations, and the World Health Organization (UN, 2022; WHO, 2022).

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